

Sexual Harassment in the Workplace

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Abstract

Sexual harassment is a pandemic, not so much an epidemic, as it occurs every day and in every setting. Despite the criminal aspect, the problem persists in the workplace. Women have been socially conditioned to be submissive to males from an early age since they have been regarded as inferior to men for generations. Sexual harassment may take many different forms. Ignoring the fact that sexual harassment has occurred since the start of civilization, it has only lately been regarded as a significant and pervasive issue, particularly at work. Researchers examined the impact of workplace sexual harassment on both male and female employees' mental health and productivity throughout this article. The study will also look at the various forms of workplace sexual harassment, as well as the reasons that may contribute to its increased incidence and prevention measures. It was accomplished by a review of the literature. The goal of the phone interviews was to find out how common sexual harassment is at work and how companies and management respond to complaints with rules, training, and action. The purpose of this research is to assist in the gathering of data that may be utilized to develop workplace sexual harassment prevention measures. Higher understanding in this sector is likely to result in increased awareness and the implementation of measures to assist avoids sexual harassment at work.

Keywords: Sexual harassment, Workplace, Gender bias, Research.

Introduction

The following research proposal investigates the gaps in the research findings and thoroughly examines and analyses the present research on the worldwide issue of workplace sexual harassment. Harassment is described as any "offensive and unpleasant" behavior (Margaret, 1996). Sexual harassment, according to the researchers, is a type of behavior that incorporates "violence and prejudice." Larsen and colleagues (Sadie E, Christopher D, & Louise F, 2018) Harassment at work is defined as a "all-encompassing collection of interconnected dark side behaviors" that impacts an employee's comfort, productivity, and safety at work while also putting the firm in legal peril. Bennett and his colleagues in their article stated that it can happen in both large and small companies (Rebecca J, Shelly, & Lauren, 2018). Being sexually harassed means being the victim of any of the scenarios listed above. Sexual harassment is determined by the criteria and conditions of each firm or society's socio-cultural agenda (Hejase, 2015).

This research proposal focuses on the issue's pervasiveness, regardless of public opinion, and offers programs and regulations to solve it. Previous study on the impact of countries that are now regulating workplace harassment by implementing new legislation or adding new parts to existing legislation to address these concerns has been clarified. However, because there is a dearth of research on how management handles workplace problems, this research proposal tries to fill the gap. The research spans 39 years, with an emphasis on the most recent papers. It focuses on what constitutes sexual harassment, as well as how the difference in men's and women's conceptions of the term leads to the persistence of such instances in the workplace. In 2021

another study was conducted which emphasized that the true amount of "sexual coercion" at work persists despite all the awareness, regulations, rules, and programs in place (Jennifer A, Shawna, Jennifer, & Karis, 2019).

The study's main purpose is to investigate the definition of the term "harassment" and what constitutes harassment at work. This study will also investigate whether victims report such instances to human resources and, if so, how management handles the problem. Another significant goal is to see if public awareness, rules, and policies have an impact on the problem's prevalence, as current methods have proven "insufficient to prevent workplace abuse" (Sara, Irina, Sami, & Eileen, 2019) Finally, once we've accomplished these objectives, we'll investigate how workplace harassment might be avoided and prevented.

As a chronic and widespread workplace problem, estimates of sexual harassment prevalence (the overall number of episodes within a given time) and incidences (the number of newly reported cases in each time) vary substantially depending on the technique employed to compute them (Paula, 2011; Julie & Alan, 2007). Despite research indicating that one to four out of every five workers have experienced sexual harassment at work (Aggarwal & Arjun, 2000), the problem has continued over time. The study investigates the core causes of workplace harassment, as well as how gender prejudices are assumed to increase the importance of womanliness. Aside from that, the study will look into the persistence of sexual harassment in the workplace. It examines how, despite abhorrence for the behavior, incidents of such inappropriate behaviors are common.

Despite the fact that workplace harassment is banned in many legal jurisdictions throughout the world, many women and a few men continue to face it in a variety of professional settings (Dobbin & Kelly, 2007). The importance of this study is based on the circumstances that lead to its occurrence.

Consequences of Sexual Harassment

Negative impact on physical and mental health

Numerous studies have demonstrated that sexual harassment is damaging to one's mental health. Racial and sexual harassment, according to preliminary research, can contribute to depression; one study revealed that one out of every ten women who experienced harassment had symptoms severe enough to be diagnosed with PTSD (Dansky & Dean G, 1997). These ramifications may last for years after the harassment has ended (Houle, Jeremy, Jeylan, Christopher, & Amy, 2011). Harassment, even if it is rare and minor, can have a significant negative influence on one's mental health and work habits (Schneider, Swan, & Fitzgerald, 1997). Regular, long-term gender-based harassment was found to raise the likelihood of long-term physical health problems as well as harmful mental health effects, according to researchers (Kimberly T, Joe, & Rebecca, 2006). Harassment can also raise the risk of workplace accidents by diverting workers' attention away from potentially hazardous tasks (Lauren, 2018). These unfavorable repercussions frequently result in high health-care costs, both mental and physical.

Fewer opportunities of on-job growth and advancement

In many firms rely on on-the-job training and mentorship from more experienced coworkers to become skilled workers and specialists in their fields. Harassment may make it more difficult for women to pursue such educational opportunities (Ariane, Cynthia, & Evelyn, 2011; Lauren, 2018). According to a recent study, harassment stifles women's career advancement in the academic sciences, engineering, and medicine by pushing them to forego tenure, drop out of crucial research projects, or resign from leadership positions in order to avoid the offender (Paula A, Sheila E, & Frazier F, 2018).

Unemployment, jobs changed by force and abandonment of established careers

For some women, unemployment is a concern because they believe they must quit a job because of sexual harassment before they can find another (Covert, 2018). According to a recent study, sexual harassment and job change are closely linked: eight out of ten women who have been sexually harassed had begun a new career within two years of the harassment (compared with just over half of other working women). The study discovered that such a job change resulted in severe financial hardship, highlighting the long-term effects of

harassment on income and professional advancement. Even when women were able to find jobs promptly after leaving their previous positions, harassment created financial hardship (McLaughlin, Heather, Christopher, & Amy, 2017). As a result of harassment, some women may decide to leave their chosen fields entirely.

Sexual harassment has different financial consequences based on the victim's job and career path, with those in higher-paying occupations losing more money than those in lower-paying occupations. Sexual harassment, on the other hand, has a substantial impact regardless of the number of missed wages: people of all income levels may rely on this money to meet fundamental necessities and attain economic stability (Roger & Henson, 1997).

Impact of Sexual Harassment on Workplaces

Workplace harassment may cost businesses a good amount of money, including legal costs whether there are formalized charges of harassment, employee turnover expenses, and lost productivity leading to increased absenteeism, lower motivation, and team disruption. While no new estimates of the business costs of sexual harassment have been released, past research indicates that these losses are high. Taxpayers bear a portion of the economic effect of sexual harassment. A 1988 evaluation of sexual harassment expenses in the United States Army indicated annual expenditures of \$250 million, which would be much higher in 2018 dollars (Faley, Deborah, Knapp, Gary A, & Dubois, 1999). The United States Merit Systems Protection Board did a study in the early 1990s that assessed the economic implications of sexual harassment in federal government employment to be \$327 million over a two-year period ("Sexual Harassment in the Federal Workplace: Trends, Progress, Continuing Challenges." , 1995).

Legal cost

High-profile sexual harassment lawsuits underscore the legal ramifications for companies that tolerate harassment (Farber, 2017). The amount of financial compensation in settlements is often kept secret, making it difficult to calculate the legal costs connected with harassment. In fiscal year 2017, the EEOC, which publishes all financial settlements it makes on behalf of employees, received \$46.3 million in monetary compensation for employees in response to sexual harassment .Because the EEOC only litigates a small fraction of all claims submitted, these costs are likely to be far lower than the actual compensation paid by employers in response to sexual harassment allegations (Rutherglen, 2015).

Employee turnover

According to research, sexual harassment in the workplace may result in increased employee turnover (Sims, Fritz, & Fitzgerald, 2005; Purl, Justin, Hall, & Griffeth., 2016). In their study of the relationship between sexual harassment and women's job success, McLaughlin, Uggen, and Blackstone (2017) reported that targets of sexual harassment were 6.5 times more likely than non-targets to change professions. The majority of the economic cost of sexual harassment is accounted for by employee turnover costs, which greatly outnumber lawsuit expenses.

Increased absenteeism

In an examination according to the 2010 National Health Interview Survey, people who reported being harassed or bullied at work in the preceding year were 1.7 times more likely than those who did not to have taken at least two weeks off work (Khubchandani, Jagdish, & Price, 2015). According to a 2016 S. Merit Systems Protection Board study (2018), roughly one out of every six employees who were subjected to sexual harassment requested sick or yearly leave as a result of the harassment.

Productivity will be lowered

Significant research suggests that workplace sexual harassment is associated with lower motivation and commitment, as well as lower job satisfaction and disengagement. Sexual harassment has a negative impact not just on the persons who are harassed, but also on those who see or hear about it, decreasing both individual and team performance. According to one study of 27 teams in a food services organization, sexual hostility: a sort of

sexual harassment that consists of plainly sexual verbal and nonverbal offensive behaviors are destructive to team processes and performance (Raver & Gelfand, 2005).

It turns out that the gender role is carried over to the work environment and is more negative for women than for men. Gutek and her colleagues called this the "sex-role spillover" (Aaron & Gutek, 1982). Serious gender imbalances in the workplace increase gender spillover. The literature also claims that many men work in integrated or non-traditional jobs (Aaron & Gutek, 1982). Women who have traditional jobs and work with men face many problems including being viewed as sheer "sexual objects" by them (Aaron & Gutek, 1982). Meanwhile, women in non-traditional professions face the problem of prominent "role deviations and attract sexual overtures". Gutek continues to argue that observed sexual harassment is less common in gender-integrated jobs, but cases still exist. As more women enter paid employment, the "old attitude" perseveres (Sahu, 2018). In addition, empirical evidence indicates that gender bias is suspected of making "femaleness more salient" (Kanter & Moss, 1978). Further studies claim that anyone "irrespective of the sexual orientation" (Fonseca, Portela, Freire, & Negreiros, 2018) can be harassed.

Studies suggest that a "climate of toleration" for sexual harassment in the work setting is an effective indicator of problem development (Buscha, 2018). Many countries now regulate workplace harassment by enacting new legislation or adding new provisions to existing legislation to address these risks. Organizational, as well as employer costs can consist of "litigation costs," employee demoralization, employee absenteeism, and counseling program costs. In spite of these well-known results, most private companies do not meet the needs of victims, as the company's top priority is generally to "avoid negative publicity" (Chappell & Martino, 2006). Large underreporting seems to be the norm, not the exception (Chappell & Martino, 2006). It is also generally believed that harassment in the workplace can lead to work environment becoming "poisoned" (Chappell & Martino, 2006).

This research proposal examines five existing theories of workplace harassment to explain the phenomenon from different angles and perspectives. Namely: Sex Role Spillover Theory, Organizational Theory, Socio-Cultural Theory, and Feminist Theory. The uncertainty of what workplace harassment, however, comprises in the included studies creates a knowledge gap throughout the field of research because people interpret the same sort of experiences much differently. This disrupts the efforts to prevent and combat sexual harassment in the workplace, thereby making it persist. Additionally, despite knowing the consequences, most private companies continue to not respond to the needs of the victims as the company's foremost priority commonly is "seeking to avoid negative publicity" (Chappell & Martino, 2006).

Prevention

Sexual harassment at the workplace is condemned as a human rights violation and sex discrimination. Without any doubt it has become the most important issue for businesses and organizations. Such irony at worksites not only lowers the level of productivity but also increases turnover and absenteeism thus causing unemployment (Desplaces & Ogilvie, 2020). As much as it is an illegal practice, it is also highly unethical. Many a time, harassment cases at workplaces go unreported as to lack of security about what meets the requirements for the harassment cases. Including lack of knowledge as how to deal and process such cases. Strict policies need to be implemented in organizations towards handling and preventing sexual harassment (Desplaces & Ogilvie, 2020). First, written and laid out rules regarding the topic should be adopted and made clear to all the employees in the form of a handbook. It should be made crystal clear as to what sexual harassment is.

In addition, a zero-tolerance policy should be obtained by both the organization as well as the reporter. The handbook must state that a fair investigation would be carried out and full confidentiality would be provided for the reporter. To emphasize this policy, training sessions and reminders must be issued regularly (Colquitt & Kleiner, 1996). The organization must always show seriousness on the topic and it should be clear to all the employees on the severity of the issue and that it would be dealt harshly. As seen in many interviews, many employees do not report sexual harassment to their management as they believe it would make no difference (Desplaces & Ogilvie, 2020). Therefore, human resource departments should be trained and prepared to handle such complaints. They should be ordered to take a serious step at such complaints (Colquitt & Kleiner, 1996).

To gain confidence and trust in their organizations by the employees, the management needs to take severe measures in resolving such complaints as well as in preventing such mishaps (Becton, Gilstrap & Forsyth, 2017). Hence, supervisors should take unannounced rounds of their worksites which would discourage and not give a chance of any such sexual coercion from occurring.

The research reveals that when any such case is reported, evidence is necessary, is asked from the reporter and is only believed on the benefit of doubt while the victim is always in the doubt. The implementation of actions presents many challenges as to how one perceives of what constitutes sexual harassment (Jensen & Kleiner, 1999). Confidentiality of the information provided by both the parties should be always preserved (Dziech & Hawkins, 2012). Those involved in investigating such cases must be neutral and experienced, documenting every step from initial to the last based on the guidelines. They should prepare a written report weighing the credibility of their findings regarding all parties involved (McQueen, 1997; Oppenheimer, 2004).

The workplace environment can be kept free from sexual harassment and assault by providing training and innovative technology by the management for mutual success and gain. Following are the recommendations to cater sexual harassment and assault in the workplace:

- Risk factor assessments should be conducted along with climate surveys to keep a check on the level of sexual harassment and assault within the organization.
- Anti-harassment policies should be developed as well as forced upon to eliminate harassment and assault. Moreover, these policies should be written in the code of conduct and should be informed about to all the employees on a regular basis (McCarthy, 2018). These policies should also be tested so that proper functioning is guaranteed. Furthermore, multiple methods should be communicated in order to report such incidents, if any.
- Management should be responsible of catering harassment incidents very strictly and employers should take serious actions against the offenders depending on the nature of the harassment and/or assault. These actions should be proper and consistent as well along with keeping a check on the offender.
- Management should further be responsible to inform and make the middle-management and supervisors' literate so that they can respond to harassment and assault cases appropriately in a proper way (McCarthy, 2018).
- Management and employers should include training sessions which include and encourage a good workplace environment and bystander intervention training.
- Labor unions should also have the same rules, regulations and reporting standards as the corporate ones have (Becton, Gilstrap & Forsyth, 2017).
- Workplace trainings should also be looked and researched upon by researchers as this may be a good way to determine that at what level the trainings help in the reduction of harassment and assault (Becton, Gilstrap & Forsyth, 2017).
- The U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, the U.S. Census Bureau, the U.S. Merit Systems Protection Board, and the Office of Personnel Management, are various agencies from where the federal government can take aid in order to carry out additional research on sexual harassment and assault. This should include adding new polls and questions to the current surveys in order to be more vigilant about such incidents.
- Training for bystander intervention, such as "Green Dot" and the new EEOC Respectful Workplaces, are promising examples (U.S. EEOC 2017) of tools and trainings that are readily available to aid employees prevent harassment and assault incidents at the workplace. Moreover, worker-led initiatives such as the "Hands Off, Pants On" campaign which was launched by union hotel employees (United Here Local 1 2018) or various policies created by the Coalition of Immokalee Workers (2018) show how stakeholders may join hands to fight against harassment.

Conclusively, it is recommended that organizations and managements should make sure that strict policies are being followed so that sexual harassment and assault incidents can be completely eliminated workplaces. Furthermore, there are only a few studies available on the impact of such efforts (like training, enforcing policies, etc.) therefore, further research is advised.

Conclusion

The findings of this study are based on a quantitative research approach and are meant to add to the growing body of evidence concerning workplace sexual harassment. The results of the poll demonstrated how widespread the topic is. The majority of individuals were significantly more comfortable sharing experiences of sexual coercion with others, according to the findings. When asked what form of harassment they had faced, the most common response was sexual remarks made over the phone. Furthermore, the majority of the participants had been harassed by their coworkers, according to the findings of the study. The replies also revealed that the majority of firms had a well-defined mechanism for reporting sexual harassment. Many people complained to management of human resources about sexual harassment, whereas others stayed silent.

According to the findings, the harasser is usually fired by management. However, one notable fact that has come to light is that when victims complained to human resources management, they were requested for evidence before the claim was investigated. It should be noticed that the bulk of responders work in the management department, providing us with a valuable insight into how the system operates. Apart from that, we discovered that a handful of the respondents did not report sexual harassment to the appropriate authority within their company. The explanation was because the management was unwilling to intervene. We discovered that sexual harassment affects almost every workplace, and that its serious consequences are felt by almost everyone. More importantly, we discovered that employees are subjected to a variety of types of sexual harassment, and that a senior individual does not always need to be held accountable. Meanwhile, according to certain research findings, numerous respondents were physically harassed at work by their coworkers. The findings of this study show that workplace sexual harassment is driven by a variety of variables, including fear of reprisal by the harasser, who may be in a strong position, victim-blaming, not being believed, and ineffective reporting procedures.

The conclusion of the study sparked yet another debate, since a small percentage of respondents who claim to work in human resources stated that they either do not take allegations of sexual harassment seriously or do not believe them. Likewise, a few others stated that they had not been taught on how to manage it, demonstrating that the handlers of these complaints are frequently uncertain of what action to take in response to the complaint, resulting in repeat incidences. The findings cannot be applied to other workplaces since this study's sample size was limited to only 28 people. This study looked into the occurrence of sexual harassment in the workplace and how efficiently administration or the relevant department dealt with it. According to the above-mentioned analysis of the research findings, the only way to provide a safe working environment for employees and reduce the occurrence of sexual harassment is to implement effective workplace policies, employee training, and a process for reporting complaints (that protects workers from retribution).

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